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Annual Report

**ANNUAL REPORT 2017- MODEL AYUSH WELLNESS CLINIC
AT PRESIDENT'S ESTATE, INDIA****Anjali BM Bakshi^{1*}, Tushita Thakur², Izharul Hasan³, Vinod Kumar Shahi⁴**^{1*}Joint Director, Rashtrapati Bhavan, New Delhi, India²Homoeopathy Consultant, AYUSH Wellness Clinic, President's Estate, New Delhi, India³Unani Consultant, AYUSH Wellness Clinic, President's Estate, New Delhi, India⁴A.D. (Ay) CCRAS & Co-ordinating Officer, AYUSH Wellness Clinic, President's Estate, New Delhi-110004**Abstract:**

The Government of India, under Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi has emphasised increased advocacy of AYUSH system of medicine and establishment of Indian systems of medicine specialty centres. Taking this vision forward, the Rashtrapati Bhavan with help of Ministry of AYUSH, Government of India; established the first AYUSH Wellness Clinic (AWC) of the country with all the five systems under one roof at President's Estate in July 2015. AWC caters to the medical needs of the President, officials of President's Secretariat and residents of the President's Estate. The mission of AWC is achieving and maintaining excellence in healthcare services through Indian system of medicine and Homoeopathy. This paper presents the annual report of work done at AWC in the year 2017. A total of 33163 patients consulted and nearly 19000 received various therapies prescribed by the physicians. The yearly AYUSH awareness workshop for residents was conducted this year too with much success. As new initiative in the year 2017- new therapies were added to the existing services in Ayurveda wing, Yoga and Naturopathy wing and Unani wing; the therapists and support staffs working at AWC were trained in First-AID and CPR and 21 research papers were published in peer reviewed indexed journals.

Keywords: Annual report, AYUSH Wellness Clinic, India, Rashtrapati Bhavan**Corresponding author:**

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VISION AND OBJECTIVE:

Honourable Prime Minister of India, Shri Narendra Modi created AYUSH ministry in November 2014 by elevation of the Department of AYUSH under Ministry of Health and Family Welfare with the vision to encourage the Indian system of medicine and Homeopathy. The Government of India has emphasised increased advocacy of AYUSH system of medicine and establishment of Indian systems of medicine specialty centres. Taking this vision forward, the Rashtrapati Bhavan with help of Ministry of AYUSH established the first AYUSH Wellness Clinic (AWC) of the country with all the five systems under one roof at President's Estate in July 2015. A dilapidated building in the President's Estate was renovated and converted into the AWC. The AWC has treatment facilities in the streams of Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha & Homeopathy. The clinic caters to the medical needs of the President, officials of President's Secretariat and residents of the President's Estate [1,2].

OUR MISSION:

Our mission is achieving and maintaining excellence in healthcare services through Indian system of medicine and Homoeopathy. The responsibility we feel for the good health of our patients is at core of our value system, attitude and daily work at AYUSH Wellness Clinic in providing comprehensive healthcare services to our valued beneficiaries. Therefore, not only curative services and therapies are available at AWC OPD but also disease prevention and positive health promotion form an integral part of available healthcare facilities.

ORGANISATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE/ ADMINISTRATION:

Manpower including consultants, therapists and MTS staff is being provided by M/O AYUSH, Government of India. The Staff for maintenance, cleanliness and security is being provided by Rashtrapati Bhavan. The infrastructure & equipment is provided by Rashtrapati Bhavan and medicines are provided by M/O AYUSH, Government of India.

SERVICE DELIVERY MECHANISM:

Patient data is maintained by the special clinic software designed by National Informatics Centre, Ministry of Electronics and IT, Government of India. Automatic OPD cards are generated by entering patient details. The detail of diagnosis and medicine/therapy prescribed is entered into the software by consulting physicians.

HUMAN RESOURCE:

The committed human resource working at the clinic includes one male and one female physician in all five wings namely Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha & Homeopathy. Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani and Siddha wings have one male and one female therapist. Yoga and Naturopathy wing has an additional Yoga therapist. Besides this, all wings have one male and one female MTS and all except Yoga and Naturopathy have a pharmacist.

OVERVIEW OF PATIENTS RECEIVING SERVICES:

An overwhelming number of patients have benefitted from the healthcare services being provided at AWC. The overview of the beneficiaries from January to December 2017 is given below in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Overview of Patient Consulted from January-December 2017

Department	New patient cases		Follow up cases		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Ayurveda	1463	802	3009	1959	7233
Yoga and Naturopathy	535	349	2516	1880	5280
Unani	1413	976	2227	2139	6755
Sidha	970	685	2033	2401	6089
Homeopathy	1411	1306	2198	2891	7806
Grand Total =	5792	4118	11983	11270	33163

*Sourced from NIC special clinic software [3]

Table 2: Overview of Therapies done from January-December 2017

Department	Total
Ayurveda	3495
Yoga and Naturopathy	8960
Unani	4627
Sidha	2349
Grand Total =	19431

*Sourced from NIC special clinic software [3]

SERVICES AVAILABLE:

Ayurveda

Consultation and medicines are available along with Ayurveda therapies including- Shirodhara, Abhyanga (Sarvanga), Abhyanga (Ekanga), Patra pinda sweda (Sarvanga), Patra pinda sweda (Ekanga), Swedana (Sarvanga), Swedana (Ekanga/ Nadi swedana), Akshi Tarpan, Katibasti, Grivabasti, Janubasti and Nasya.

Yoga & Naturopathy

Consultation is available along with Yog Chikitsa (Asana, Pranayam, Meditation), Naturopathic diet therapy, Masso therapy (Manual full / partial), Mud therapy (Full/ Partial), Steam therapy (Full/ Partial/ facial), Hydrotherapy (Spinal bath, Spinal spray, Foot & Hand, With pack, Enema), Potli/ Poultice, Foot Reflexology and Mustard Pack.

Unani

Consultation and medicines are available along with Unani therapies including Hijamat (Wet cupping), Hijamat (Dry / Gliding/ Fire cupping), Dalak, Mechanical massage chair, Mechanical riding machine, Hammam, Local massage with local steam, Facial steam, Muscle stimulation (TENS), Fasd and Takmed.

Siddha

Consultation and medicines are available along with Siddha therapies including Varmam & Thokkanam, Thuvalai, Podi Thimiral Therapy, Vedhu, Patru, Pugai, Otradam & Kizhi and Nasyam.

Homoeopathy

Consultation and medicines are available in Homoeopathic department. The department is popular among patients for Gynaecological disorders including menstrual disorders, fibromyoma uterus, polycystic ovarian disease, leucorrhoea, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, menopausal syndrome; Genito-urinary diseases including urinary tract infection, renal calculi and benign hypertrophy prostate; Skin diseases including chronic eczema, lichen planus, hair loss including alopecia areata and

diffuse hair loss, chronic urticaria, ringworm, psoriasis, vitiligo; Respiratory diseases including allergic rhinitis, chronic sinusitis, chronic tonsillitis, bronchial asthma and chronic bronchitis.

COLLABORATION OF AYUSH SYSTEMS:

AYUSH Wellness Clinic is a platform for cross-talk and collaboration between different AYUSH systems of treatment. Cross-referrals are made to achieve better and faster clinical results for the benefit of patients. Several patients have benefitted by integrating: Ayurvedic medicines & Siddha therapies in treatment of Arthritis and Back pain; Homeopathic medicines & Yoga in Bronchial asthma and chronic sinusitis and Unani therapy and Homoeopathic medicines in High Blood Pressure; Homoeopathic medicines & Siddha therapies for Diffuse Hair Loss, Cervical Spondylosis and Frozen Shoulder. The physicians working at the AWC continue to collaborate for patient benefit and publish this valuable data.

INFORMATION, EDUCATION & COMMUNICATION (IEC):

Communication is the key to generating awareness on prevention as well as motivating access to treatment, care and support. Recognising this, IEC material is available at a designated area near the OPD registration counter and respective pharmacies. There is also an interactive touch screen kiosk in the OPD wing that informs the clinic beneficiaries about the different AYUSH systems, their strength and treatment options available. Besides this, regular AYUSH awareness workshops are conducted at the AWC premises for the residents of President's Estate that are the clinic beneficiaries. The AYUSH awareness workshops conducted in the year 2017 include the following:

- **Diabetes: cause, treatment and prevention through Homoeopathy & Yoga-** The workshop highlighted the cause, prevention and treatment of type 2 diabetes through Yoga and homoeopathy. Specially prepared Type 2

prevention tips including dietary prevention, exercise, lifestyle and Yoga was given to patients in form of flyers.

- Pain management through Varmam Therapy in Siddha-** The word 'varmam' denotes energy flow in the body and the points where this energy resides in the body are identified as varmam points [4]. The basic objective of the varmam therapy in Siddha is to stimulate these points using palms, fingers, etc., to cure diseases. It is beneficial in nerve disorders, chronic arthritis, sleep disorders, facial palsy, migraine and asthma. Through this workshop the residents were educated about varmam therapy and a live demonstration to teach self varmam therapy for common ailments was also given.
- Health benefits of Cupping Therapy: Unani-** Cupping therapy is Unani regimental therapy where therapist puts special cups on skin for a few minutes to create suction. The suction and negative pressure provided by cupping encourages blood flow, helps relieve pain, remove "heat" and pull out the toxins from tissues. It is useful in relieve back and neck pains, stiff muscles, anxiety, migraines, and hypertension [5]. The residents were educated regarding health benefits of cupping therapy with talk and live demonstration in the workshop.
- Preventing and treating Joint diseases through Ayurveda-** In Ayurveda, osteoarthritis (Sandhigat Vat) is considered a disease of malnutrition that tends to affect vulnerable joints (due to previous injury or infection, congenital reasons etc). The root cause of osteoarthritis is often at processes of digestion, or Agni. In Ayurveda, rheumatoid arthritis (Ama Vat) is seen as a disease of toxic accumulation and immune malfunction. In the case of rheumatoid arthritis, there is a very high level of accumulated Ama (hence the name) and in many cases, a considerable amount of excess heat (or Pitta) [6]. Prevention of joint diseases as per Ayurvedic concept of doshik imbalances was emphasised in this workshop.
- Managing Lifestyle disorders with Naturopathy-** Lifestyle diseases are associated with the way a person or group of people lives. Lifestyle diseases are common these days due to modern lifestyle, tobacco and alcohol addiction, lack of nutrition, stress, lack of

adequate exercise and lack of rest to mind and body. These disorders include atherosclerosis, heart disease, and stroke; obesity and type 2 diabetes. The use of Naturopathy for preventing and treating lifestyle disorders was highlighted in this workshop.

The residents attended the workshops in large numbers and benefitted from the health information given to them. The workshop feedback was taken in form of a specially designed feedback form which was filled by 4-5 residents after each workshop.

NEW INITIATIVES IN 2017:

1. New Therapy Additions

To cater to the needs of patients visiting AWC, new therapies were added to the existing services in Ayurveda wing, Yoga and Naturopathy wing and Unani wing. The therapies added include- Matravasti, Churna Pinda Sweda (Sarvanga), Churna Pinda Sweda (Ekanga), Udvartan, Lepana (Ekanga) in Ayurveda wing, Hip bath in Yoga & Naturopathy wing and Fire Cupping, Facial Cupping, and Cautery in Unani wing. The removal of warts, moles and external piles through cauterization is simple, painless OPD procedure that does not require anaesthesia or blood loss and is being well appreciated by the patients.

2. Staff Training in First Aid and CPR

The therapists and support staffs working at AWC were trained in First-AID and CPR during the year 2017. The course was conducted in the AWC premises by First-AID experts from St. John's ambulance. Being a clinic cum therapy centre; this training was conceptualized at AWC as to make the employees more safety aware, spot hazards and potential incidents before they occur. First-AID and CPR training proved to be a great team building exercise. It has given employees the confidence and ability to treat themselves, their family and patients effectively in an incident, injury or illness.

3. Research Publications

A total of 21 research papers have been published till date in peer reviewed indexed journals. Collaborative studies published include the following:

- Success stories in form of a collection of case reports by all physicians working in the clinic.
- A case study published on the results of integrating Unani and Ayurveda therapies and Homoeopathic medicine for the management of High Blood pressure.
- Three clinical studies published highlighting collaborative results of combining Homoeopathic

medicines & Siddha therapies for Diffuse Hair Loss, Cervical Spondylosis and Frozen Shoulder.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVES:

1. Expanding therapy services to accommodate the needs of the patients and give maximum benefit at OPD level.
2. Furthering the scope of AYUSH awareness workshops by conducting group health talks for smaller gender/age specific groups for better engagement, understanding and patient benefit. For example health talk on menstrual hygiene for pubertal girls, antenatal care for pregnant women and their attendants, managing exam stress for students etc.
3. Addition of counselling services for patients and their attendants with special focus on mental health.
4. Starting an AYUSH library facility at the premises which will include general interest books as well as journals on AYUSH system of medicine.
5. Patient feedback form for constant feedback and suggestions from clinic beneficiaries.
6. Continued focus on publication both individually and as a collaborative team effort by the physicians working at AWC.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

1. Press Information Bureau, Government of India, President's Secretariat. President of India to inaugurate AYUSH wellness clinic at President's Estate. Available at: <http://pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=123676>. Accessed on 09/01/2018.
2. Press Information Bureau, Government of India, President's Secretariat. President of India Inaugurated Ayush Wellness Clinic & a Restored Clock Tower at President's Estate. Available at: <http://pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease.aspx?relid=123746>. Accessed on 09/01/2018.
3. NIC special clinic software for AYUSH Wellness Clinic, President's Estate. Available at <http://164.100.23.71/ayush/ViewCardRegistrationsReport.aspx>. Accessed on 09/01/2018.
4. Varmam therapy. Available at <http://siddham.in/treatment-of-various-ailments-through-varmam-kalai-or-marma-treatment>. Accessed on 09/01/2018.
5. Unani regimental therapies. Available at <http://ayush.gov.in/about-the-systems/unani/therapeutics/regimental-therapy>. Accessed on 09/01/2018.
6. Ayurvedic concept of joint diseases. Available at <http://www.mudita.institute.com/articles/ayurvedicmedicine/arthritis.html>. Accessed on 09/01/2018.